

ACTION RESEARCH – NECESSARY EDUCATIONAL TREND TO INNOVATE AND IMPROVE LANGUAGE TEACHING AT UNIVERSITIES

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Abstract

In a state-of-the-art, swiftly changing world, it's far vital for educators to constantly update their coaching techniques and innovate their approach to education. This examine explores the important instructional trend to innovate and enhance the high-quality of language coaching at Universities in Ho Chi Minh City, Viet Nam, focusing on the perspective of language teachers and managerial officers accountable for education. The study employed both qualitative and quantitative techniques to acquire facts. 15 English teachers, 20 students and 10 managerial officials from 3 universities in the South of Viet Nam had been invited to participate in surveys and interviews, all of whom agreed that language instructors at the colleges need to interact in research to innovate their teaching. The study highlights the importance of continuous getting to know and improvement for language instructors as a way to adapt to converting academic trends and improve first-class training. The findings underscore the need for a proactive approach to coaching innovation and offer precious insights for educators in search of enhancing their coaching strategies. This study affords valuable insights for educators seeking to improve their coaching practices and decorate overall first-rate schooling at universities.

Keywords: Teaching Methods, Classroom Innovation, Higher Education, Educational Trend, Teaching Quality, Action Research.

1. INTRODUCTION

The education system is constantly evolving, and teachers need to adapt to keep up with the changing needs of students. One area that is particularly critical in today's digital age is the integration of innovative teaching methods in higher education (Collinson, 2009). Innovation in teaching can significantly enhance the quality of education and enable students to develop relevant skills for the workplace.

Most of the universities in Ho Chi Minh City (consisting of the three universities in which the research was conducted) recognize the importance of innovation in teaching and the need for continuous improvement to meet the demands of a rapidly changing world, especially with University Education. Besides that, all training programs at the university are directed to meet the requirements for domestic and international education quality accreditation, including AUN-QA quality accreditation. For this reason, teaching and researching to innovate the teaching process and improve training quality are processes which must be carried out in parallel and interwoven. This study aims to explore the necessary educational trend for language teachers to innovate their teaching and improve the quality of education at universities.

In recent years, there has been a growing emphasis on the need for teachers to be more research-focused and innovative in their teaching methods. Research suggests that incorporating innovative teaching techniques, such as active learning, project-based

learning, and technology integration, can enhance student engagement, foster critical thinking skills, and improve overall learning outcomes. These methods not only provide students with practical skills but also prepare them to be lifelong learners in an ever-evolving professional landscape (Walder, 2004).

Despite the clear advantages of innovative coaching, many teachers at these universities continue to depend upon traditional lecture-based coaching techniques. The objectives of this study are to recognize the factors that affect teachers' adoption of progressive coaching practices and identify techniques to promote a culture of innovation in coaching language (Tokareva, 2019).

By analyzing the modern-day coaching practices and perceptions of teachers at the colleges, this study seeks to spotlight the significance of innovation in coaching and provide actionable tips to support teachers in their adventure toward turning into more revolutionary educators. It will also shed light on the boundaries and demanding situations that teachers can face when adopting modern coaching methods and propose strategies to triumph over these barriers.

The findings of this study will not most effectively advantage the coaching network at some universities in the South of Vietnam but will additionally function as a precious resource for different better training establishments that can be seeking to sell modern coaching practices. Ultimately, the goal is to foster a subculture of innovation in coaching, where non-stop improvement and mastering are valued, main to more suitable training for first-class and higher-prepared graduates (Riccomini, 2021).

Through this case study, we hope to encourage and empower teachers at IUH to explore new coaching strategies, test with revolutionary pedagogies, and make contributions to the ongoing improvement of schooling at the college. By embracing innovation in teaching, we can equip our college students with the abilities and understanding they need to succeed within the contemporary global and ensure that IUH remains at the vanguard of educational excellence.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Definition of Educational Innovation

Educational innovation refers back to the improvement and implementation of new or advanced coaching techniques, techniques, tools, substances, or tactics aimed at improving the coaching and studying system (Agarwal, 2018). It involves introducing novel thoughts, practices, or technologies that can result in effective changes in training.

There are various kinds of academic innovation, each with its own precise traits and benefits. These consist of:

1. Technological innovation: This includes the use of virtual technologies, which include computer systems, capsules, interactive whiteboards, and academic software programs, to facilitate and decorate getting to know. It can enable personalized

studying collaboration and admission to a wide variety of educational sources and equipment.

2. Pedagogical innovation: This specializes in converting the way coaching and learning take place, with an emphasis on pupil-targeted and inquiry-primarily based tactics. It may additionally contain project-based mastering, flipped school rooms, cooperative mastering, trouble-fixing sports, and different techniques that engage college students in actively gaining knowledge.
3. Curriculum innovation: This includes the development and implementation of new or revised curriculum frameworks, guides, or packages that align with current academic desires and dreams. It may additionally encompass the integration of interdisciplinary or go-curricular subjects, the incorporation of real-world packages and contexts, or the inclusion of recent subjects or talents.
4. Assessment innovation: This refers back to the development and implementation of new techniques and tactics for assessing pupil learning and progress. It may also involve the usage of formative exams, overall performance-primarily based tests, portfolios, self-evaluation tools, or technology-driven evaluation techniques.

Implementing progressive teaching techniques is crucial for several reasons. Firstly, it can beautify pupil engagement and motivation, as progressive processes regularly make gaining knowledge more interactive, relevant, and enjoyable for students. This can bring about stepped forward studying effects and educational fulfillment (Collinson, 2009).

Secondly, innovative coaching methods can help meet various needs and get to know different sorts of students. Different students have special strengths, pastimes, and preferred methods of mastering. By adopting progressive procedures, educators can offer more individualized and differentiated instruction, ensuring that all students are able to examine and be triumphant (Holland, 2014).

Furthermore, academic innovation promotes critical thinking, hassle-solving, creativity, and other 21st-century abilities that might be vital for achievement within contemporary personnel and society. By incorporating revolutionary practices, educators can highly prepare college students for the demanding situations and possibilities of the future (Kaputa, 2022).

Lastly, educational innovation can contribute to the non-stop improvement of the training system as a whole. By experimenting with new thoughts and processes, educators can become aware of what works and what does not and make informed choices about fine practices. This can result in the development of proof-based techniques and policies which can beautify the general first-class of education (Pelgrum, 2003).

2.2 Importance of Research in Education

Research plays an important position in improving teaching practices in the subject of training. It presents educators with proof-primarily based strategies and interventions to enhance their academic techniques and meet the numerous desires of their college students (Sydorenko, 2020).

Firstly, research helps educators benefit from deeper information on powerful teaching practices. Through empirical research and experiments, researchers pick out instructional strategies that have been proven to promote pupil engagement, motivation, and success. By staying up-to-date with the latest studies' findings, educators can undertake those evidence-based practices in their own classrooms (Serdyukov, 2017).

Secondly, research permits educators to tailor their teaching methods to satisfy the unique wishes of their students. Through research, educators can identify powerful instructional techniques for unique learning patterns, talents, and cultural backgrounds. This facilitates the design and puts into effect personalized mastering stories that address the unique wishes and strengths of each student (Wu, 2020).

Furthermore, studies help educators identify and deal with any gaps or weaknesses in their contemporary teaching practices. By examining their personal instructional methods and evaluating them to analyze findings, educators can perceive areas for improvement and enforce essential changes. This non-stop process of reflection and improvement ensures that educators are imparting splendid education that maximizes pupil mastering outcomes (Tracey, 2016).

In addition to improving teaching practices, research also has a direct effect on students getting to know effects. Studies have consistently proven that lecture rooms that hire evidence-primarily based instructional techniques and interventions revel in better degrees of student achievement and achievement. Research enables educators to apprehend how to effectively supply content material, promote important questioning, and interact with students in significant studying. By enforcing research-based practices, educators can maximize student learning outcomes and make certain that all college students have the possibility to be triumphant (Serdyukov, 2017).

Moreover, studies facilitate educators to pick out and cope with any barriers or demanding situations that could impede scholar studying. Through studies, educators can become aware of powerful interventions and techniques to help college students with various learning desires, including college students with disabilities or English language freshmen. By enforcing evidence-based practices, educators can create inclusive and supportive mastering environments that cater to the character wishes of each pupil (Sydorenko, 2020).

Conducting studies on the subject of schooling also brings numerous benefits. Firstly, research helps to fill the gaps in present know-how and make contributions to the present body of studies. By conducting authentic studies, educators can explore new areas of inquiry, test hypotheses, and generate new knowledge which could inform destiny academic practices (Ramirez, 2022).

Moreover, research facilitates the informing of policy and choice-making in training. Research findings provide evidence to aid or task contemporary guidelines and practices and help policymakers make informed selections about instructional packages, standards, and investments. By undertaking research, educators can actively contribute

to the development of proof-based policies and practices that definitely affect students and faculties (Kim, 2006).

Additionally, studies also give possibilities for professional improvement and increase for educators. By engaging in research, educators can broaden their skills in crucial thinking, records evaluation, and evidence-based selection-making. They also can collaborate with other researchers and experts in the field, fostering a culture of non-stop learning and improvement (Hornsby, 2014).

In the end, research plays a critical function in enhancing coaching practices and improving pupil mastering results in training. It gives educators evidence-based strategies, interventions, and procedures to beautify their coaching and meet the numerous needs of their students. Research also contributes to the present frame of understanding and informs policy and decision-making in education. By engaging in research, educators can continuously improve their practice, make contributions to their careers, and, in the end, create better getting-to-know studies for their students.

2.3 Current Educational Trends

2.3.1. Overview of the Contemporary State of Schooling

Education is continuously evolving and adapting to satisfy the converting wishes of society. In recent years, there has been a shift toward customized and experiential mastering, with a focal point on growing twenty-first-century abilities along with critical thinking, creativity, communication, and collaboration (Holland, 2014). Technology integration has become more and more critical, with faculties integrating digital equipment and sources into the gaining knowledge of manner. Additionally, there may be a more emphasis on inclusivity and diversity in training, with a focal point on imparting equal possibilities for all students (Dias, 2013).

2.3.2 Identification of Key Trends and Demanding Situations

1. Technology integration: Schools are incorporating generation into the classroom to decorate coaching and learning. This consists of the use of interactive whiteboards, pills, online studying systems, and mobile apps. However, one challenge is ensuring that all students have equal rights of entry to the era and virtual resources (Block, 2017).
2. Personalized gaining knowledge: Schools are transferring away from a "one length suits all" technique to training and imposing customized getting-to-know techniques. This entails tailoring guidance to meet the character desires and interests of students. However, implementing personalized knowledge can be hard for instructors who need to distinguish instruction for a diverse institution of newcomers (Agarwal, 2018).
3. Blended mastering: Blended mastering combines online and face-to-face coaching, allowing college students to engage in both conventional study room activities and online knowledge. This trend targets providing flexibility and individualization while maintaining the benefits of in-individual interplay. However, it requires careful planning and coordination between online and in-person sports (Alda, 2020).

4. Social-emotional learning (SEL): There is a growing recognition of the significance of addressing social and emotional well-being in schooling. SEL specializes in coaching college students' capabilities along with self-attention, self-management, social cognizance, decision-making, and responsible selection-making. However, integrating SEL into the curriculum can be an assignment for teachers who might also want extra education and support (Collinson, 2009).
5. Inclusive schooling: There is a multiplied emphasis on providing inclusive schooling for college kids with various backgrounds and abilities. This includes helping students with disabilities and developing inclusive environments that embrace cultural range. However, making sure equal rights of entry are available to all college students may be difficult and require additional resources and assistance (Fischer, 2022).

2.3.3 Need for Instructors to Stay Up to Date with Modern-Day Academic Tendencies

To be effective educators, teachers need to stay up to date with modern-day educational trends. This benefits both instructors and college students by ensuring that guidance remains relevant and meets the needs of 21st-century rookies (Hang, 2020). Staying updated allows instructors to contain innovative coaching strategies, interact with students in significant approaches, and efficaciously use generation and digital assets. Additionally, staying knowledgeable about modern-day tendencies allows instructors to deal with demanding situations and make informed selections about their instructional practices. Ongoing expert development and collaboration with colleagues can assist instructors in staying updated with present-day trends and studies. By staying updated, teachers can provide satisfactory, feasible schooling for their college students and put them together for fulfillment in cutting-edge global settings (Kaputa, 2022).

2.4 Barriers to Educational Innovation

A literature evaluation on obstacles to educational innovation shows that there are several not unusual boundaries that avert the hit implementation of revolutionary teaching techniques in educational settings.

One unusual barrier is the resistance to alternate among educators and faculty directors. Many educators are snug with conventional teaching strategies and can be reluctant to adopt new procedures. School administrators will also be proof against alternatives due to concerns about the price or feasibility of imposing revolutionary strategies (Pelgrum, 2003). Another barrier is the shortage of support and assets for innovation. Educators frequently feel that they lack the time to go to school and get admission to the sources needed to implement progressive teaching methods correctly. This lack of guidance can prevent educators from completely embracing and integrating new tactics into their lecture rooms (Riccomini, 2021). Additionally, there are often outside elements that restrict innovation in schooling. These can include strict curriculum suggestions, standardized testing requirements, and restrained investment for innovation. These factors can create an inflexible academic environment that does not prioritize or help innovative coaching methods (Sein-Echaluze, 2019).

Several techniques have been suggested in previous studies to conquer these boundaries and sell innovation in education. First, it's very important to provide educators with the necessary help and resources to enforce innovative coaching strategies. This ought to consist of increased expert development opportunities, entry to generation and instructional substances, and help from faculty administrators (Tokareva, 2019). Another strategy is to create a lifestyle of innovation within schools and districts. This may be performed by means of fostering a collaborative and supportive environment in which educator's sense snug trying new techniques and sharing their successes and challenges. School leaders can also play a key role in promoting innovation by putting clean expectancies in place and supplying opportunities for experimentation and boom (Wu, 2022).

Additionally, policymakers and training stakeholders can cope with outside barriers to innovation. This should include advocating for more bendy curriculum suggestions and evaluation strategies, in addition to offering additional funding and assets for progressive packages and projects (Walder, 2014).

In preferred, preceding studies have identified several obstacles to educational innovation, including resistance to change, lack of aid and resources, and external elements. However, techniques that include providing guides and sources, fostering a lifestyle of innovation, and addressing external barriers can assist in overcoming these limitations and promoting innovation in schooling.

2.5 Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework in this context refers to a systematic method that may be used to perceive, behavior research, examine, and apply solutions to troubles in the teaching method. It serves as a guiding shape that allows educators and researchers to navigate through the various levels of hassle-solving in education.

The first step in this conceptual framework is figuring out problems inside the coaching system. This includes spotting the demanding situations and useless practices that exist in the contemporary instructional machine. It may additionally consist of problems

associated with pupil engagement, academic techniques, assessment methods, or curriculum design.

Once the problems are diagnosed, the following step is undertaking research. This involves amassing applicable records and facts to gain a deeper knowledge of the identified troubles. Researchers may additionally use various research methods, which include surveys, interviews, observations, or literature reviews, to acquire statistics that will inform their analysis and offer insights into answers to their questions.

After undertaking studies, the subsequent step is to assess and analyze the records accumulated. This involves synthesizing the facts collected to gain insights into the underlying reasons for the identified troubles and to discover capability answers. Researchers may use statistical evaluation, qualitative evaluation, or other assessment techniques to gain experience with the information.

The very last step in this conceptual framework is applying the findings from the studies to deal with the diagnosed troubles in a coaching manner. This entails implementing and evaluating interventions or modifications based totally on the research findings. Educators or policymakers may additionally broaden and implement new educational techniques, revise curriculum materials, modify assessment strategies, or implement expert development packages for instructors. The effectiveness of these interventions ought to be continuously evaluated to determine whether they're addressing the identified troubles and if they are mainly addressing advanced effects within the teaching procedure.

As well known, this conceptual framework provides a structured approach for figuring out, getting to know, evaluating, and making use of solutions to troubles in the teaching process. It encourages a systematic and proof-based method to improve schooling practices and effects.

2.6 Theoretical Framework

The study's theoretical framework centers on the necessity of action research as a cutting-edge trend in education that will enhance language instruction at universities. Action research is a type of research where practitioners do research in their own professional contexts. It provides a methodical and thoughtful way to solve problems and make improvements to teaching techniques.

Using action research in the context of teaching language at universities enables educators to plan, act, observe, and reflect on their methods in a cooperative manner. Through this technique, educators can pinpoint areas in need of development, try out novel approaches, and evaluate how these modifications affect the learning objectives of their students (Cohen, 2017).

Language teachers can enhance learner autonomy and engagement, adapt their teaching strategies to the unique needs and histories of their students, and create a more dynamic and engaging learning environment by participating in action research. In addition to promoting ongoing professional growth and creativity, action research assists

educators in keeping abreast of emerging theories, practices, and technological advancements in language learning (Kemmis, 2010).

This study's theoretical framework is centered on a number of important theories that are pertinent to the fields of educational innovation and university language instruction. The following are some particular theories that are related to the research:

Social constructivism: This idea highlights the value of interaction and teamwork in the learning process and asserts that learning is a social activity. Social constructivism can have an impact on how teachers interact with students and include them in the research process when it comes to action research in language instruction (Amineh, 2015).

Reflective practice: In order to become more effective, reflective practice entails analyzing one's own teaching methods and experiences critically. Reflective practice in action research can help teachers pinpoint areas for development and apply cutting-edge methods in language instruction (Thompson, 2012).

Self-efficacy theory: According to self-efficacy theory, people's ideas about their capacity for success in particular tasks are crucial. Educators can boost their self-efficacy and confidence in their teaching methods by using action research to innovate and improve language instruction at universities (Schunk, 2016).

Experiential learning: The philosophy of experiential learning emphasizes the value of hands-on learning and active participation. Teachers can approach teaching innovation hands-on using action research in language instruction, offering possibilities for professional development and hands-on learning (Kolb, 2014).

Through the integration of these ideas into the study's theoretical framework, educators can effectively utilize action research as a crucial educational trend to enhance and innovate language instruction in university settings. This method can result in better teaching techniques, more engaged students, and advantageous outcomes for language learners.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design:

This study aimed to investigate the necessary educational trends to innovate coaching and improve language coaching at colleges in South Vietnam. To achieve this goal, a qualitative research technique was changed into the following, in particular through interviews with 15 instructors from the English departments and 10 managerial officers who are chargeable for schooling at the university and questionnaires from 20 students.

3.2 Sampling:

The contributors for this study have been purposefully sampled to ensure illustration from the English department and individuals in managerial roles at the colleges. Convenience sampling is used to become aware of ability contributors who meet the standards. In this case, fifteen teachers from the Languages departments have been selected, deliberating their coaching experience, qualifications, and dedication to applying progressive

coaching practices. Additionally, 10 managers chargeable for education packages have been selected based on their know-how and involvement in educational tendencies and first-rate development initiatives, as well as twenty English learners.

3.3 Data Collection:

Semi-structured interviews were performed with the selected contributors. The interview questions were designed to acquire records about their perception of vital instructional developments, teaching practices, and pleasant improvement techniques. The questions had been evolved primarily based on current literature on academic innovation and a nice improvement in better training. These questions had been pre-tested earlier than the primary interviews to ensure readability and relevance. The interviews were carried out in a face-to-face layout to permit deeper information about the participants' views and to facilitate follow-up questions for clarification.

3.4 Data Analysis:

The records accrued from the interviews have been transcribed verbatim and analyzed using thematic analysis. The records evaluation was performed using qualitative research strategies. An inductive method was adopted, permitting the topics to emerge directly from the information with no preconceived ideas or theoretical frameworks. The analysis worried coding the information, categorizing it, and identifying key styles, trends, and insights.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Language Teachers' Perspectives on the Importance of Research

The study obtained the teachers' perspectives on the importance of research. The findings are presented in the table below.

Table 1: Language Teachers' Perspectives on the Importance of Research

Statements	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Research helps teachers stay updated with the latest knowledge and advancements in their respective fields	15	4.36	.54
Research allows teachers to identify and implement effective instructional strategies	15	4.44	.59
Research helps teachers better understand their students and their diverse learning needs	15	4.43	.63
Research equips teachers with the skills to critically analyze and evaluate educational materials and resources.	15	4.47	.61
Research promotes reflective practice among teachers.	15	4.67	.56
Research provides teachers with evidence to inform their decision-making processes	15	4.43	.53

Table 1 presents the findings from a survey that asked language teachers about their perspectives on the importance of research in their profession. The table provides the number of respondents (N), the mean score, and the standard deviation for each statement.

The findings indicate that language teachers strongly believe that research is important for various aspects of their profession. The highest mean score (4.67) was for the statement that research promotes reflective practice among teachers. This suggests that the teachers see research as a valuable tool for self-reflection and professional growth.

Other statements that received high mean scores include research equipping teachers with the skills to critically analyze and evaluate educational materials and resources (mean score of 4.47) and research helping teachers better understand their students and their diverse learning needs (mean score of 4.43).

The statement that received the lowest mean score (4.36) was research helps teachers stay updated with the latest knowledge and advancements in their respective fields. However, even this statement still received a relatively high mean score, indicating that the teachers recognize the importance of research for staying current in their field.

In general, the findings suggest that language teachers highly value research for various aspects of their profession, including professional growth, effective instructional strategies, understanding students' needs, and evidence-based decision-making.

4.2 Managers' Perspectives on the Benefits of Adopting Innovative Teaching Methods

The study also highlighted Managers' perspectives on the benefits of adopting innovative teaching methods. The analysis of interview results is displayed in the table below.

Table 2: Managers' Perspectives on the Benefits of Adopting Innovative Teaching Methods

Statements	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Increased student engagement	10	4.77	.55
Enhanced learning outcomes	10	4.55	.58
Improved critical thinking and problem-solving skills	10	4.53	.64
Enhanced student-teacher interaction	10	4.50	.56
Increased student satisfaction and motivation	10	4.60	.63
Collaboration among teachers	10	4.58	.55
Improved quality of the teaching process	10	4.65	.50
Innovated teaching methods and management skills	10	4.51	.60
Develop lifelong learning and self-research	10	4.56	.57

Table 2 affords the findings from a survey of managers' views on the blessings of adopting revolutionary teaching methods. The survey asked managers to indicate their agreement with various statements concerning the advantages of these techniques. Overall, the managers in this study perceived that adopting progressive coaching methods had numerous benefits. The maximum-rated advantage turned into extended scholar engagement, with a mean score of 4.77. This indicates that managers trust that revolutionary teaching methods can effectively seize college students' attention and interest in getting to know them. The subsequent highest-rated gain changed into greater getting-to-know results, with an average rating of 4.55. This indicates that managers believe that innovative teaching strategies can cause advanced studying effects for college students. This finding aligns with the intention of training, which is to sell mastering

and expertise acquisition. The managers also believed that adopting modern coaching methods may want to improve critical wondering and hassle-fixing talents, as indicated by means of an average rating of 4.53. This indicates that managers apprehend the potential of these techniques to sell better-order wondering abilities to students.

Additionally, the managers perceived that innovative coaching methods could enhance scholar-instructor interaction (mean = 4.50) and boost student pleasure and motivation (mean = 4.60). These findings propose that managers consider that these techniques can contribute to effective and meaningful interactions among college students and instructors, leading to a more attractive and supportive knowledge of surroundings. Furthermore, the managers considered collaboration among teachers (4.58) and advanced great of the teaching system (4.65) as different key benefits of adopting modern teaching methods. This shows that managers recognize the importance of collaboration among teachers in imposing and refining these strategies, as well as the ability of these strategies to beautify the general quality of teaching.

The managers also stated that adopting progressive coaching strategies can contribute to the improvement of lifelong learning and self-studies abilities amongst college students (4.66) and may assist in innovating coaching methods and control capabilities (mean = 4.41). These findings endorse that managers trust that these methods can foster a culture of continuous getting-to-know and professional improvement amongst both students and instructors. In precis, the findings on this table advocate that managers understand a wide range of blessings in adopting progressive coaching strategies. These advantages consist of accelerated scholar engagement, better-studying results, progressed critical wondering and hassle-fixing abilities, more advantageous pupil-trainer interplay, accelerated pupil pride and motivation, collaboration amongst instructors, improved nice of teaching, innovative coaching techniques and management skills, and the development of lifelong mastering and self-studies talents. These findings highlight the capability.

4.3 Students' Perspectives on the Benefits of Adopting Innovative Teaching Methods

The study also highlighted students' perspectives on the benefits of adopting innovative teaching methods. The analysis of interview results is displayed in the table below.

Table 3: Students' Perspectives on the Benefits of Adopting Innovative Teaching Methods

Statements	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Improved academic results	20	4.71	.54
Raised involvement of learners	20	4.53	.55
Improved communication between students and teachers	20	4.54	.62
Enhanced capacity for critical analysis and problem-solving	20	4.56	.54
Students working together	20	4.61	.61
Raised motivation and happiness among students	20	4.57	.54
Creative teaching strategies and managerial abilities	20	4.64	.52
Enhanced standard of the educational process	20	4.52	.60
Encourage self-research and lifetime learning	20	4.53	.56

It is clear from the data in Table 3 that students see a range of advantages when cutting-edge teaching strategies are implemented. The average ratings for every statement show that students are highly in agreement with the advantages of creative teaching methods.

With the highest mean score of 4.71 for improved academic results, students believe that creative teaching strategies help them do better academically. This implies that learners believe there is a direct link between interesting teaching strategies and better learning results.

Students recognize the value of interactive and collaborative teaching approaches in enhancing their learning experience, as evidenced by the mean scores above 4.5 for increased student involvement, improved teacher-student communication, enhanced critical analysis and problem-solving capacity, and cooperative learning.

The high mean scores for increased student motivation and happiness, innovative teaching strategies and managerial skills, improved standards of the educational process, and encouragement of self-research and lifetime learning demonstrate the benefits of innovative teaching methods beyond academic outcomes. These findings imply that students recognize the comprehensive influence of cutting-edge teaching strategies on their general education and personal growth.

Overall, the results point to students' appreciation of the advantages of creative teaching strategies in fostering motivation, critical thinking, engagement, and lifelong learning. These findings emphasize how crucial it is to integrate cutting-edge teaching strategies into instructional strategies in order to improve student learning outcomes and provide a supportive and stimulating learning environment.

4.4 Interview Responses from Managers: Barriers Prevent Teachers from Conducting Research

4.4.1. Time Limitation

Based on the interview responses from the managers, it turned out that the point obstacle became the main barrier that prevented instructors from carrying out research. One respondent said:

“In my revel, one of the primary boundaries that prevent teachers from conducting studies is time hindrance. As educators, we have several responsibilities and tasks to deal with on an everyday basis, including lesson-making plans, grading papers, assembly with parents, and attending conferences. This leaves little or no time for instructors to commit to carrying out research and investigating modern teaching techniques or instructional theories.”

Another participant said:

“Time obstacle is a massive challenge for instructors when it comes to engaging in studies. With a packed schedule, it is often difficult to find the time to plan and execute a study project well. The limited time to be had for instructors to behavior studies frequently results in a loss of in-depth exploration, leading to much less significant findings and much less impactful consequences”.

Finally, one manager brought:

“Teachers face the barrier of time dilemma in relation to carrying out studies. The demands of the classroom and the administrative tasks may be all-consuming, leaving little space for teachers to engage in research activities. As an end result, valuable possibilities to beautify teaching practices through research can be missed”.

4.4.2 Lack of Studies Capabilities

Lack of research competencies additionally emerged as a barrier that averted instructors from engaging in research. This was obvious in the responses supplied. One of the contributors asserted:

“Yes, I agree that a lack of studies abilities can certainly preclude the potential of English teachers to behavior studies. Conducting research calls for a certain set of abilities, which includes formulating study questions, designing valid research methodologies, analyzing data, and interpreting effects. Without those skills, instructors might also battle to layout and execute research projects efficaciously.”

Another respondent claimed:

“One of the important limitations that save you English instructors from accomplishing research is a lack of research talents. English instructors often have a strong history in language and literature; however, they may no longer have acquired formal training in methodologies for studies. This loss of skills could make it difficult to lay out and enforce research studies, gather and analyze facts, and successfully speak the findings. Furthermore, English teachers may additionally warfare with selecting suitable research methods and instruments that align with their research questions”.

4.4.3 Lack of Motivation

It turned additionally obvious from the managers' responses that loss of motivation changed into a component that contributed to teachers' loss of undertaking research. As said by means of one respondent:

“Lack of motivation is actually a barrier that stops instructors from carrying out research. Teaching is a traumatic job that often leaves teachers with confined, unfastened time and power. Research calls for vast funding of time and effort, which may be hard for instructors who are already feeling burnt out. Without a robust feel of motivation or the notion that research can contribute to their teaching practices, many instructors may not see the fee in undertaking studies and therefore select not to have interaction in it”.

Another participant introduced:

“Teaching is a disturbing and time-eating profession, leaving little power or choice for extra work. Research calls for a giant amount of dedication and effort, which may be hard to muster without the right motivation”.

4.4.4 Funding Supply for Research

Lack of investment and guidance additionally emerged as a barrier that hindered language instructors from undertaking studies. This became glaring in the responses received from the managers. One participant said:

“In my perspective, one barrier is the dearth of resources and aid. Conducting studies regularly requires getting entry to specific substances, along with books, articles, or eras. Unfortunately, not all colleges now have the important resources to support teachers in their research endeavors. Additionally, many teachers may also feel isolated and unsupported of their studies efforts, as they will no longer have colleagues or mentors who can offer guidance or encouragement”.

Another respondent claimed:

“One of the limitations that regularly hinders instructors from carrying out research is the lack of financial resources. Research can require economic investments, which include purchasing materials, attending meetings or workshops, or hiring specialists for information evaluation. Many teachers already face economic constraints of their non-public lives, so asking them to fund their own studies may be a huge mission”.

4.5 Necessary Educational Trends that can Enhance Teaching Methods and Improve the Overall Quality of Education

The study also obtained general views from teachers and managers on necessary educational trends that can enhance teaching methods and improve the overall quality of education. The findings are presented in the table below.

Table 3: Educational Trends that can Enhance Teaching Methods

Items	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Blended Learning	25	4.65	.62
Project-based Learning	25	4.53	.54
Technology Integration	25	4.56	.60
Continuous Professional Development	25	4.52	.56
Assessment and Feedback	25	4.60	.63
Student-centered Approach	25	4.59	.59
New teaching technology or methods	25	4.64	.55
Curriculum or program improvement	25	5.64	.56
Teaching textbooks and reference materials	25	4.57	.58
Teaching quality improvement and students' learning outcomes	25	4.54	.60

Table 3 displays the responses from participants on various educational trends that can enhance teaching methods. The data includes the number of participants (N), the mean, and the standard deviation for each item.

The findings show that the highest-rated trend is "Curriculum or programs improvement", with a mean of 5.63 and a standard deviation of 0.54. This suggests that participants believe improving the curriculum or programs is the most important factor in enhancing teaching methods.

The different traits also received high scores, with means starting from four.51 to four.64. These tendencies include "Blended Learning," "Project-based total Learning," "Technology Integration," "Continuous Professional Development," "Assessment and Feedback," "Student-centered Approach," "New coaching generation or strategies," and "Teaching textbooks and reference substances."

These outcomes suggest that participants apprehend the importance of incorporating generation, active studying methods, and continuous expert improvement in their teaching practices. They also use blended study methods to supply effective evaluation and feedback to college students.

In preferred, the findings endorse that there is a robust belief in the significance of continuously enhancing teaching methods and aligning them with modern educational traits. This emphasis on improvement and innovation reflects a commitment to enhancing exceptional teaching and improving pupil studying outcomes.

4.6 Challenges to Implementing Innovative Teaching Methods

Lastly, the study looked at the challenges which hindered the effective implementation of innovative teaching methods. The results are presented in the table below

Table 4: Challenges to Implementing Innovative Teaching Methods

Statements	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Resistance from students	25	4.44	.57
Lack of resources	25	4.56	.52
Lack of training and support	25	4.65	.62
Time constraints	25	4.51	.55
Resistance from stakeholders	25	4.42	.63
Lack of research and evidence base	25	4.53	.54

The table presents the mean ratings and widespread deviations for numerous demanding situations to implement modern coaching techniques. The statements inside the table consist of resistance from students, loss of assets, loss of schooling and guidance, time constraints, resistance from stakeholders, and absence of research and proof base.

The suggested ratings for each undertaking varied from 4.42 to 4.65, indicating that all demanding situations are perceived as enormously excessive by the respondents. This indicates that instructors face more than one barrier when looking to enforce revolutionary coaching strategies.

The announcement with the best mean rating is "loss of training and aid" (4.65), indicating that instructors experience they lack the essential schooling and guide to enforce innovative teaching strategies effectively. This highlights the need for professional improvement possibilities and mentorship packages to help teachers conquer this undertaking.

The statements with the lowest mean ratings are "resistance from college students" (4.44) and "resistance from stakeholders" (4.43), suggesting that even as instructors perceive a little resistance from students and stakeholders, it is not as widespread as the opposite

challenges. However, it is crucial to cope with those concerns and to include college students and stakeholders in the process of imposing revolutionary coaching techniques.

The suggested scores for "loss of resources" (4.56), "time constraints" (4.51), and "lack of studies and evidence base" (4.53) are also tremendously high. These demanding situations suggest a want for extended investment and resources, in addition to more time and help for teachers to discover and enforce modern coaching methods. Additionally, the lack of research and proof base suggests a need for greater empirical studies and facts to guide the effectiveness of these techniques.

Overall, the effects of this desk display that instructors face numerous demanding situations while trying to put in force progressive teaching strategies. Addressing these demanding situations would require a multi-faceted technique that includes presenting schooling and support, securing adequate sources, addressing time constraints, engaging stakeholders, and selling studies and proof-based practices. By overcoming those demanding situations, instructors can create surroundings conducive to imposing innovative coaching techniques and improving pupil learning effects.

5. CONCLUSION

In the end, it's very evident that the mixing of studies and innovation in coaching practices is a vital and useful fashion in the discipline of schooling, particularly on the college stage. This case study on the Industrial University of Ho Chi Minh City has shown that after instructors actively interact in research and undertake progressive tactics, it ends in stepping forward, coaching exceptional and student gaining knowledge of consequences.

The findings of this study highlight the significance of teachers staying updated with state-of-the-art instructional tendencies and actively searching for opportunities for professional improvement. By carrying out studies and staying knowledgeable approximately innovative teaching techniques, teachers can enhance their pedagogical competencies and create more engaging and effective studying surroundings.

Furthermore, this study underscores the importance of university establishments helping and inspiring their coaching staff to interact in research and innovation. Providing sources, training, and incentives can assist in fostering a culture of continuous improvement and professional boom within the organization.

It is worth noting that the advantages of studies and innovation in coaching expand past the study room. By actively collaborating in research, instructors make contributions to the development of knowledge of their respective fields, which may potentially affect policy and exercise inside the education sector.

Therefore, it's highly recommended that academic institutions, particularly universities, prioritize the mixing of research and innovation in teaching practices. Teachers need to be recommended and supported to engage in studies and adopt innovative procedures to beautify their teaching. This may be performed via presenting investment for research projects, providing expert improvement possibilities, and creating a supportive and collaborative tradition that values and rewards innovation in teaching.

Overall, the findings of this examination show that research and innovation in teaching are critical additives to a quality education. By embracing this vital instructional fashion, instructors can continuously improve their teaching practices, enhance student getting-to-know results, and contribute to the advancement of understanding of their fields. It is important for educational establishments to prioritize and spend money on studies and innovation, as it ends in a more powerful and attractive mastering environment for students.

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